

Table S1: Description of soil profiles in grove and savanna in the Mole National Park, Ghana

Grove Soil Profile Pit 1

Horizon number	Depth (cm)	Symbol	Description
1	0-6	A	Dark brown (75 YR 3/2), moist; fine sandy loam; moderate medium subangular blocky; friable, slightly sticky slightly plastic; many fine interstitial pores; common very fine, few fine, medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
2	6-12	AB	Dark brown (75 YR 3.5/3), moist; fine sandy loam; moderate medium subangular blocky; friable, slightly sticky slightly plastic; many fine interstitial pores; few very fine, medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
3	12-41	Bt	Reddish brown (2.5 YR 4/4), moist, sandy clay loam; few (3%) quartz stones; moderate coarse subangular blocky; friable, sticky plastic; few clay + iron coating on pedfaces and long pores; many fine interstitials few planar voids, channels and vughs; few fine medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
4	41-55	Btcs 1	Dark reddish brown (2.5 YR 3.5/4), moist; sandy clay loam; few (<2%) medium quartz gravel; weak medium granular; friable sticky plastic few clay + iron coatings on pedfaces and along pores; abundant (60%) hard, irregular iron and manganese nodules; many fine interstitial pores, few fine medium and coarse roots; diffuse smooth boundary
5	55-80	Btcs 2	Dark reddish (2.5 YR 3.5/4), moist, sandy clay loam; black broken manganese mottles; few (< 2%) medium quartz gravel; massive; sticky plastic many interstitial pores; abundant (7%) hard irregular iron and manganese nodules; few fine, medium and coarse roots

Soil classification: **Pisoplinthic Plinthosol**

Grove Soil Profile Pit 2

Horizon number	Depth (cm)	Symbol	Description
1	0-18	A1	Very dark greyish brown (10 YR 3/2), dry, very dark greyish brown (10 YR 2.5/1), moist, loam; strong fine and medium granular soft, very friable, slightly sticky slightly plastic; many fine interstitial pores; common very fine, few fine, medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
2	18-40/48	A2	Brown (7.5 YR 4/2), dry, very dark greyish brown (7.5 YR 3/2), moist, sandy clay loam; few quartz gravel and stones; moderate medium subangular blocky; hard friable, sticky plastic; many fine interstitial pores; few channels and voids; few very fine; fine medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
3	40/48-60	Btcs	Reddish brown (2.5 YR 4/4), moist; few fine distinct (10 YR 6/7), moist, yellowish brown mottles; sandy loam, few (4%) quartz gravel and stones; friable, sticky plastic; common faint clay + iron coatings around nodules; abundant 75% hard and slightly hard irregular iron nodules many fine interstitial pores, few channels and vughs; very few, very fine, fine roots
4	60-80	Btcsm	Red (2.5 YR 4/6), moist; common destem yellowish brown (10 YR 6/7), moist, mottles; sandy clay loam; few quartz gravel and stones; massive sticky plastic; dominant (80%) slightly hard irregular iron nodules; many fine interstitial pores few channels and vughs very few fine roots

Soil classification: **Pisoplinthic Plinthosol**

Grove Soil Profile Pit 3

Horizon number	Depth (cm)	Symbol	Description
1	0-15	Acs	Dark brown (7.5 YR 3/2), moist, sandy loam; moderate fine granular; friable, slightly sticky plastic; many (20%) hard iron and manganese concretions and nodules; many fine interstitial pores; many very fine, common fine few medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
2	15-28	BAcs	Dark brown (7.5 YR 3/4), moist, loamy sand; moderate fine and medium granular, very friable; non-sticky non-plastic; many (20%) hard iron and manganese concretions and nodules; many fine interstitial pores; few medium channels; common very fine; few fine medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
3	28-54	Btcsm	Strong brown (7.5 YR 4/6), moist, sandy clay loam; massive hard, friable, coatings in pores; common (2%) hard iron and manganese nodules; many fine interstitial pores; few channels; few very fine, fine and medium roots; diffuse smooth boundary
4	54-76	Btcsm2	Strong brown (7.5 YR 4/6), moist, few fine distinct red (2.5 YR 4/6), moist mottles; sandy clay loam; massive; hard, friable sticky plastic; few faint clay plus iron coatings in pores; common (15%) hard iron and manganese nodules; many fine interstitial pores few channels; few very fine; fine and medium roots; diffuse smooth boundary
5	76-93	Btcsm3	Strong brown (7.5 YR 4/6), moist, few fine distinct red (2.5 YR 4/6), moist, mottles; massive hard, friable, sticky plastic; few faints clay plus iron in pores; common hard iron and manganese nodules; many fine interstitial pores; few channels; pieces of charcoal, few very fine, fine and medium roots

Soil classification: **Petric Plinthosol**

Savanna Profile Pit

Horizon number	Depth (cm)	Symbol	Description
1	0-20	A	Dark brown (7.5 YR 3/2), moist; loamy fine sand; few (3%) fine quartz gravels; moderate fine and medium granular; very friable non-sticky non-plastic; few (3%) iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores; common very fine few fine, medium and coarse roots, clear smooth boundary
2	20-30	BA	Dark brown (7.5 YR 3/4), moist, sandy loam; few fine quartz gravels; weak fine and medium sub-angular blocky; very friable slightly sticky slightly plastic; few (5%) iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores; few very fine, fine, medium and coarse roots; clear smooth boundary
3	30-55	Bt1	Reddish brown (5 YR 4/4), moist; sandy clay loam; few fine quartz gravels, moderate fine and medium granular; friable, sticky plastic; few faint clay plus iron in pores; common (10%) iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores, few medium channels; few very fine, few medium and coarse roots; gradual smooth boundary
4	55-75	Bt2	Reddish brown (5 YR 4/4), moist, sandy clay loam; few fine gravels; moderate medium sub- angular blocky; moderate fine and medium granular, friable, stick plastic; few faint clay plus iron in pores; common (10%) iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores, few medium pores, few medium channels; few very fine, fine medium and coarse roots; gradual smooth boundary
5	75-103	BC	Strong brown (7.5 YR 4/6), moist; few distinct yellowish red (5 YR 4/6), moist mottles; sandy clay loam; stratified; friable sticky plastic; common (10%) iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores; few medium channels and vughs; few very fine; fine, medium and coarse roots; diffuse smooth boundary
6	103-133	C1	Strong brown (7.5 YR 4/6), moist, common fine distinct yellowish red (5 YR 4/6), moist and faint pale brown (10 YR 6/3), moist mottles, sandy clay loam; stratified; friable sticky plastic; common (6%) sub-rounded iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores few channels and vughs; few very fine and fine roots; diffuse smooth boundary
7	133-145	C2	Strong brown (7.5 YR 4/6), moist, common distinct yellowish red (5 YR 4/6), moist and faint pale brown (10 YR 6/3), moist, mottles; sandy clay loam; stratified friable sticky plastic; few (3%) sub-round iron concretions; many fine interstitial pores; few channels and vughs; few very fine and fine roots

Soil classification: **Chromic Lixisol. Chromic Lixisol described here amidst Plinthosols of the vast adjoining savanna**

Table S2b: Species in the regeneration layer in the belt transect in the Mole National Park

Transect square:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	
	Open savanna										Grove										Intruding savanna					Grove										Savanna					
<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i>	12	13	3	9	6	3	22	101	11	3	2	20	5	20	7	5	4				11	2	9	12	37			2	2		1	1		1	2			1	2	1	18
<i>Combretum ghasalense</i>	3	3	1	5		3	5	6	1	2															1														5	7	3
<i>Ptilostigma thoningii</i>		1				1	1																		2														1		
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	1	6	7	1	2		3	1	1	4	5	2												1	11	10		9	5										6	7	29
<i>Grewia mollis</i>	1		2	6	3		6		2		1	1	4	6	3	1	1	4	3	1			1		1	1			1	2	1	4							11	1	
<i>Ximania americana</i>	1		2	2	5					1																		1	7	1	2								1		1
<i>Diospyros mespiliiformis</i>	1			6					2		1		11	3	2	3	1	1		3	4				2	2				1	6	3	6	4	2	6	12	10	7	1	
<i>Grewia lasiodiscus</i>			1	8		1	1			1			3		1	6			1		1		3						1		4	4		1			1	2	1	5	3
<i>Secureniga virosa</i>				6					1		2	2	3		1		1	1	1	2				4	2	1		1	3	4		3						1	3	1	
<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i>	8	3	4	4	2	1		2	1		2								1	1				2	1	1			1						1			1	7	7	1
<i>Strycnos innocua</i>			1	1					1		1	2	4		7	2	1	2	1	1	2									9	5	1	2	4	17	6		1	1	1	
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>									1	1			1	5		3				1	1			2	1			2		12	9	2				11	9	3	1		
<i>Cassia sieberana</i>			2						1		1																												1		3
<i>Acacia. Spp.</i>				4				1													6		69	15		1		3	33	3	1						1	8			1
<i>Sarcocephalus latifolius</i>																																						1			
<i>Lanea acida</i>																								1							1		2				1				
<i>Combretum nigricans</i>									1		1										1							1								1					2
<i>Detarium microcarpum</i>																									1				1												
<i>Gardenia aquala</i>	3																												1											2	
<i>Kegilia africana</i>	2	14	5	5	13	7																																		1	
<i>Bridelia ferruginea</i>																																									1
<i>Terminalia avicennioides</i>	30	29	6	6	3	1		3																																	3
<i>Lanea barteri</i>																				1																					
<i>Azelia africana</i>			1		2	1				1																															

Figure S1: C/N ratios of different soil organic carbon and nitrogen fractions at Mole